

Cultural sensitivity in mental health nursing in neurology: A theoretical model.

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Abstract

The concept of cultural sensitivity is located within the tradition of anthropology and the history of colonisation and immigration in Australian society. This history serves as a foundation for analysing how cultural issues were mainly uncritically introduced into the field of nursing. The author of this essay contends that current interpretations of diversity in nursing and health care policy have a tendency to conceal, disregard, and ultimately perpetuate ideas of racial supremacy. Recent transcultural nursing studies are used to demonstrate how arbitrary and ahistorical features are assigned to various cultural groups. This viewpoint promotes political neutrality and avoids challenging the discriminatory practises ingrained in fundamental social relations because it is legitimated in terms of cultural sensitivity.

Keywords: Transcultural nursing, Nursing education, Cultural sensitivity tool.

Introduction

Cultural sensitivity is the understanding, awareness, and acceptance of different cultures and other people's cultural identities. It is sometimes referred to as cross-cultural sensitivity or simply cultural awareness. It is connected to cultural competence (the abilities required for successful cross-cultural communication) and is seen as the stage before achieving cultural competence, however it is a more commonly used phrase than cultural competence. Travellers and employees can successfully navigate a new culture with which they are interacting when they are sensitive to it on a personal level [1].

Cultural sensitivity, which combines intercultural dialogue and other abilities, combats ethnocentrism. In many countries, there are minority groups that include native peoples and immigrants from different cultures. These groups also make up the workforce, educational institutions, media, and organisations of all kinds. Are aware of the need to respect these communities' cultures. At all levels, training is becoming more and more a part of the curriculum for both employers and students. In multicultural cultures, the training may also be given to immigrants to inform them about other minority groups, as well as to expatriates working abroad. The training is typically geared toward the majority culture [2].

Definitions and aims

There are several ways to define cultural sensitivity. Fundamentally, it is the understanding, sensitivity, and acceptance of other cultures. It comprises acceptance of variety and "the willingness, competence and sensitivity required to understand persons with various backgrounds." It is crucial to

note that it "refers to the skill set obtained by this learning, as well as being aware that cultural differences and similarities between people exist without giving them a value." Cultural sensitivity is the acceptance of those differences and the denial of the superiority of one's own culture. Cultural awareness is the knowledge that there are several different cultures, each with its own attitudes and worldviews. The phrase "cultural competency" is frequently used to refer to the knowledge and abilities needed to demonstrate cultural sensitivity, especially in the workplace. Flexibility is necessary for cultural sensitivity. Literature search of international databases, both popular and scholarly, discovered that the phrase was more commonly used [3]. The definition that was chosen for cultural sensitivity was based on an analysis of the sources that were discovered in the same search: "Cultural sensitivity is employing one's knowledge, consideration, understanding, respect, and tailoring after realising awareness of oneself and others and encountering a diverse group or individual."

Any society will have a wide range of cultural variety, including variations related to socially or economically disadvantaged groups, ethnicity, sexual orientation, handicap, values, and cultural norms. Cultural sensitivity is important for all of these. Ideological or practical concerns might be used to support cultural sensitivity. Former United Nations Secretary-General Kofi Annan promoted cultural sensitivity as a crucial virtue in the contemporary world [4].

Factors that affect cultural sensitivity

Cultural sensitivity can be impacted by specific factors. These variables can include gender, religion, ethnicity (race), or national origin (language). Age, education, socioeconomic

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situation, sexual orientation, and physical and mental difficulties are additional factors to consider. Previous research has found a link between multicultural encounters and cultural sensitivity.

Cultural self-assessment

Understanding how one's own behaviour and views may influence others is crucial. The most significant activities are typically those that are taken for granted.

For instance, cultural differences might be seen in physical distance or touch during social encounters. Although contact is a crucial prerequisite for our well-being, people in different cultures receive varied amounts of touch on a daily basis. While others don't, some cultures stand closer to one another, make more eye contact, speak louder, and use touch more frequently [5].

In the dominant culture

By knowing about different cultures and how diverse styles and expectations may differ from one's own in various areas, from ethical, religious, and social attitudes to body language and other nonverbal communication, cultural awareness and sensitivity helps one transcend their own ethnocentrism. One aspect of cultural competence is cultural sensitivity, which influences ethnocentrism and other aspects of culture. The benefits of increasing cultural awareness include: Improved

communication allows for more effective engagement between those involved and better results or interventions for the client or customer.

Conclusion

Study results may be referenced in designing future in-service and cultural care education programs for community health nurses to improve healthcare quality for new immigrants.

References

1. O'Donohue W, Benuto L. The many problems of cultural sensitivity. *Scientific Review of Mental Health Practice*. 2010;7(2).
2. Foronda CL. A concept analysis of cultural sensitivity. *J Transcult Nurs*. 2008;19(3):207-12.
3. Anakwenze O. The cultural sensitivity continuum of mental health interventions in Sub-Saharan Africa: A systematic review. *Soc Sci Med*. 2022:115124.
4. Sublette E, Trappler B. Cultural sensitivity training in mental health: Treatment of Orthodox Jewish psychiatric inpatients. *Int J Soc Psychiatry*. 2000;46(2):122-34.
5. Larson D, Milano GM, Lu F. Religion and mental health: The need for cultural sensitivity and synthesis. *Clinical methods in transcultural psychiatry*. 1998:191-210.